

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17529547

The Many Colours Of Law; Interrogating The Realities And The Absurdities

Dumgbara Nda Smart Torbari ESQ, LLB, BL, LLM,

Principal Attorney, Divinity Attorneys, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

Email: divinityattorneys2002@gmail.com

Phone: 08064661995

ABSTRACT

The world over, the idea of law is a basic idea. The thirst for law is a constant thirst. The desire to unravel the mystery called law remains as burning as the desire of man to live. To this end, law seem to have swallowed the other aspects of knowledge including philosophy of which law is merely a branch. This creates the picture of a child being larger than the parents. This is why the definition of law and the struggle to define law is an unending one. This is why in the midst of other concepts such as morality, religion, justice, the state, law stands so taller, stronger and more vocal than them all, a kind of the status and statue of a leviathan. This paper seeks to unravel the mystery of the very idea of law and its position or standing in face of other concepts such as religion, sovereignty, morality, justice and the state. This paper discusses these concepts within the parameters of law and exposes the lacuna while asserting or emphasizing the need to preserve the boundaries. The paper adopts the doctrinal approach in interrogating the different perspectives. The paper concludes that while law is the basic idea, the relevance of other ideas must not be ignored or jettisoned if the good of society is to be upheld. The paper recommends various ideas to strengthen the bond between law and other concepts in the quest for a society of just laws, just men and just administration of just laws.

Keywords: Colours, Law, Interrogating, Realities, Absurdities

1. INTRODUCTION

The question as to what actually constitutes or becomes the law in a given legal order has been the subject of much academic, intellectual and jurisprudential debate over the years. Theorists and legal commentators have dissipated much intellectual energy in the voyage of discovery as to who actually is the law giver or law maker. Is it parliament, that is, the legislature, or the executive or the judiciary that actually makes or manufactures what is called law in the society? This argument continues to gain currency inspite of express constitutional provisions¹ donating the power of law making to the legislature².

This is the position in the constitutions of most, if not all constitutions of democratic states.³ Under the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), the three essential powers of the state are clearly defined and their specific functions are also clearly outlined⁴.

The law is well settled that the constitution is the organic or basic law of the land and its provisions are supreme⁵. Nonetheless, it does appear that often times, judicial pronouncements seem to dictate what the law actually is, and not merely what the legislature and the executive stamp has decreed as law. The most

* Dumgbara Nda Smart Torbari Esq, LLB, BL, Principal Attorney, Divinity Attorneys, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

divinityattorneys2002@gmail.com

¹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).

² Section 4 CFRN 1999.

³ U.S Constitution, South African Constitution all have this common provisions.

⁴ Section 4 – donates legislative powers and functions to the legislature, while section 5 donates executive powers and functions to the executive, and judicial powers are vested in the judiciary under section 6.

⁵ Section 1 sub-section 1 CFRN.

profound pronouncement on the role of these three organs of government is found in the decision of the Supreme Court of Nigeria in the case of *Inakoju vs. Adeleke*⁶, where Tobi, JSC held,

“The legislature is the custodian of a country’s constitution in the same way that the executive is the custodian of the policy of government and its execution, and also in the same way that the judiciary is the custodian of the construction or interpretation of the constitution. One major role of a custodian is to keep under lock and key the property under him so that it is not desecrated or abused. The legislature is expected to pet the provisions of the constitution like the way the mother pets her day-old baby, the legislature is expected to abide by the provisions of the constitution like the way the Clergyman abides by the Bible and the Imam abides by the Koran”.

From the foregoing therefore, it follows that what is law is what actually emanated from the floor of parliament and nothing more pretentious. But is that the reality in our present experience? I am inclined to say NO. This is because, in several situations, the judex have upturned the decrees of parliament and written new decrees which eventually wears and carries the power of law. This is in line with the postulation of Justice Holmes⁷ of the U.S Supreme Court, who indeed is the founder or Chief Proponent of the Realist School of Jurisprudence to the effect that it is *“what the judges will say or do and nothing more pretentious”* that actually is the law, and not what the legislature has rolled out of their Chambers. As we shall see later in the course of this work, the judex have upturned or invalidated several legislations or laws or statutes validly passed by the parliament and that becomes the law and nothing more or less. Thus, an investigation into this development is necessary as it will enable a proper and more comprehensive enlightenment on the subject.

2. THE CONCEPT OF LAW

The question what is law, is controversial as the question, what is life. This is because every person has his or her perception of what law is and what law is not. And these perspectives are usually largely informed by the individual’s background, such as education, philosophy, religious, social or moral inclinations or prejudices. Thus, law has been defined variously thus:

*“That portion of the established thought and habit which has gained distinct and formal recognition in the shape of uniform rules backed by the authority and power of government”*⁸.

*“The body of principles recognized and enforced by public and regular tribunals in the administration of justice”*⁹.

*“The system of rights and obligations which the state enforces”*¹⁰.

*“The body of principles recognized and applied by the state in the administration of justice”*¹¹

*“We ordinarily use the term “law” to mean a body of rules to guide human action”*¹²

*“Any kind of rule or canon whereby actions are framed”*¹³.

Different schools of thought have long emerged as to the question what is law. The positivists see law as the command of the sovereign backed by sanctions. The sociological school sees law as the instrument of social engineering. The Marxists see law as the weapon by which the rich oppress the poor. The realists see law as the pronouncement of the judge. The naturalists see law as the divine instructions of God to man. The historical theorist defines law from the customs and traditions of the people. We shall undertake greater discourse of these perspectives in the course of this work.

Law, to this researcher is nothing but the body of rules by which a particular state, society, organization is governed or administered.

The original intention of God was for man to live quietly, peacefully and happily in a society devoid of sin, acrimony and evil. But that was not to be. The seed of sin and therefore evil sprang up in man and the desire to antagonize one another took the centre stage. Greed and the desire to be in control became pronounced in man. So, society became a field for the survival of the fittest or the arena for struggle for control. Gradually it became evident that there is the need to impose some measure of restrictions on the behaviour of man in society. This is where the idea of law was given birth to.

⁶ 1999 (2007) ALL NWLR (PT. 353) 3 @ 123, Tobi JSC – delivered the bad judgement.

⁷ Hon. Justice Holmes served in the U.S Supreme Court as a judge for 30 years.

⁸ Wilson

⁹ Pound

¹⁰ Green

¹¹ Salmond

¹² Appadurai – The substance of politics, oxford, 2004, P. 59

¹³ (Hooker - Ecclesiastical Polity)

In any community, there will develop set and customary ways of carrying on social activities, which save time and avoid friction. They form a sort of unwritten code, enforced by parental and religious authority or by the pressure of public opinion. Some of these customs however may become so important for general welfare that stronger pressure than social authority or opinion must be brought to bear on those members of the community who act in violation of accepted social standards.

Whenever any community, acting through its government undertakes to apply such pressure by fixing a penalty for violation, then such customs cease to be purely social and become political. They become the law of the land. They are virtually commands, ordering or prohibiting certain actions, disobedience to which involves a penalty inflicted by the government¹⁴. This is how the law came into being; this is the very idea of law in human society.

The failings of man, the need to preserve man and society and guarantee orderliness, peace and progress combined together to generate the idea of law. Law became a necessity for the survival of man and society. Law is not just an instrument introduced into society for the fun or entertainment of it or for the purposes of mass control. Law as an instrument or a machine for society's good has so many functions. In other words, law performs very important or vital roles in the society. We shall look at some.

- i. Law and order. The presence of law in society is primarily to secure the order of that society. In the absence of order, there will be disorder and chaos. Where there is chaos, there is bound to be confusion and strife. According to Prof. Wigwe SAN¹⁵, "*Every society needs social order, without this normal life activities cannot go on...even during war situations, there are still some basic laws that must be observed between warring parties*"¹⁶. This follows that it is the presence of law and of course its enforcement that ensures the maintenance of the social order. It stops the citizens from acting or doing things according to their private or selfish desires, but only according to law.
- ii. It is by the instrumentality of law that justice is attained or can be actualized. The cardinal aim of law is to create a society where social justice is done to all on the parameters of equality, fair play and the common good. It is the presence of law that entitles an aggrieved person to seek justice in the form of one remedy or the other from the ordinary law courts. Therefore, it could be safely said that law provides that solid foundation upon which the search for and attainment of justice is premised. It must however be added that only just laws and a just administration of just laws that guarantees justice. It is therefore incumbent on the law makers to ensure the enactment of just laws, just as it is incumbent on the judex to ensure a just interpretation of laws and necessity becomes laid upon the law enforcement agencies of government to ensure a just enforcement of laws. This means that the concept of justice through just laws is a function of the three principal organs of the government.
- iii. Laws confer sovereignty to the people. Laws make the people the master, not the servant. Law makes the people lords, not slaves. Before the emergence of law, princes, lords, fiefs, kings, pirates ruled in absolutism and were practically worshipped as gods by the people. But when law came, power changed hands. Sovereignty was transferred to the people, for example, the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 declares,

It is hereby, accordingly declared that: sovereignty belongs to the people of Nigeria from whom government through this constitution derives all its powers and authority.¹⁷

This clear statement of the law defines unquestionably the source and the custodian of sovereignty in Nigeria. Similar provisions are replete in most modern constitutions¹⁸. Only in military dictatorships, do sovereignty still reside in the maximum ruler or dictator.
- iv. Law determines the certainty and durability of legal systems. By law, what is law is made certain, such that what is not law becomes certain also. Therefore, law removes assumptions of what is law and what is not law. Law also prescribes procedures for doing a thing, e.g. amendment of laws and rules of procedure. This makes for certainty and durability. Our constitution¹⁹ provides for the mode of altering provisions of the constitution, which makes it impossible for people who control

¹⁴ A Appadurai – The substance of politics, Oxford 2004, P. 59.

¹⁵ Prof. C.C. Wigwe SAN is the Dean Faculty of Law, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

¹⁶ C.C. Wigwe, jurisprudence address/theory, Princeton, 2024 @ 97

¹⁷ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Section 14 (2) (a).

¹⁸ Ibid S. 14 (2) (b)

¹⁹ Ibid S. 9

government to use their influence and power to change the goal post every time the opposition wants to score.²⁰

- v. Law provides quick and adequate resolution of disputes. Law guides judges in adjudication in deciding the rights and obligations of the parties to a dispute. Since it is not within the province of judges to make laws, but to interpret laws, laws are a verifiable instrument for settlement of disputes in society. Without law, dispute resolution would be individualistic, chaotic and acrimonious.
- vi. Law directs the mode of formation and change of government. It is by the instrumentality of law that governments are formed, principally through general elections as provided under electoral laws. It is also by the machine of law that governments are changed within certain time limits or durations. The Nigerian constitution²¹ forbids any form of change of government besides or outside what is expressly provided in the constitution. The difference however occurs where there is a military overthrow of government through coup de tats.²² Where this happens, the constitutional provision, especially as it relates to change of government are usually abrogated or suspended.²³ Even at that, the military decree becomes the new law by which the new government legitimizes its authority and sustains its hold on power.

3. THE CONCEPT OF SOVEREIGNTY

The idea of the sovereign is fully of political and legal origin. This is because the sovereign is clothed with legal authority without which he is a mere citizen. The Black's Law dictionary²⁴ defines sovereign to mean a person, body or state vested with independent and supreme authority; the ruler of an independent state. It goes further to define a sovereign state to mean a state that possesses an independent existence, being complete in itself, without being part of a larger whole to whose government, it is subject. The dictionary proceeds to define sovereignty to mean supreme dominion, authority or rule²⁵

From the foregoing, it becomes clear that sovereignty encompasses the idea of a definite personality or body having supreme or absolute dominion or rulership over others within a defined territory or particular legal order. The sovereign therefore is a supreme commander whose words automatically translates into law that must be obeyed. He is the biggest and most dreaded masquerade in a political territory or legal order. Sovereignty resides in him and in him alone, therefore he is not just the master of ceremony, he is the owner and controller-general of the ceremony. The person in whom sovereignty lies is the sovereign. He is the grand commander²⁶ of the political and legal space and his wishes becomes the law by which others are governed.

In dictatorships, sovereignty resides in the maximum ruler or a special body so created and controlled by him²⁷. The revolutionists who seize state power from elected political leaders will immediately issue proclamations and decrees vesting sovereignty in the leader of the revolution or in a body headed by him²⁸. However, in constitutional democracies, it is usually expressly stated in the constitution that sovereignty resides in the people²⁹.

The Nigerian constitution declares;

*"Sovereignty belongs to the people of Nigeria from whom government through this constitution derives all its powers and authority"*³⁰.

Thus, in democracies, sovereignty resides in the people. They therefore are vested with power and authority to hire and fire any government. This is made possible through the holding of periodic elections wherein the people vote to choose those who will form the government at any point in time. It must however be said or added that even in democracies, there has been instances where the civilian leaders stage a civil coup to

²⁰ The view of Prof. C.C. Wigwe in his book, jurisprudence and legal theory, Princeton 2024 @ 99

²¹ Section 1, sub-section 2 CFRN 99

²² The government of Shagari was overthrown on December 31st 1983 via a broadcast by General Sani Abacha

²³ Decree 1 of 1984

²⁴ 11th ed. P. 1680

²⁵ n.27 P. 1681

²⁶ Positivists call him the uncommanded commander; he is the political superior who rules over political inferiors.

²⁷ During the Buhari/Idiagbon dictatorship, sovereignty vested in the supreme military council, in the Babangida dictatorship sovereignty vested in the Armed Forces Ruling Council.

²⁸ By decree 1 of 1984, the Buhari dictatorship abrogated the 1979 constitution and conferred maximum power on the SME.

²⁹ Constitution of the FRN 1999

³⁰ No. 39, S. 14 (2) (a)

remain in power against the clear wishes of the people. This they do by stage managing or rigging elections to turn the tables in their favour contrary to the popular vote. This has led to series of election litigations in which courts have in a number of cases declared the actual winner of the elections and ordered the impostors out of office. Therefore, the idea of sovereignty is dependent on the type of regime in place and the political correctness of the actors at the time.

4. LAW AND THE STATE.

The discussion of law and the state wears more of a political colouration than a legal concept. This is because the influence of the state over the law is tremendous, in the same way the influence of law over the state appears overwhelming. The question is, can the state survive without the law, and can the law exist independently of the state? The next question is, is the state a creation of law or the law a creation of the state? The next question is, what is the purpose of the state and the purpose of the law³¹.

The idea or concept of the state appears to be of divine origin.

The Bible declares,

*“Let every soul be subject unto higher powers. For there is no power but of God: the powers that be are ordained of God. Whosoever therefore resisted the power, resisted the ordinance of God: and they that resist shall receive to themselves damnation”*³².

The Bible also presents God as the original supreme law giver:

*“And God spake all these words saying, I am the Lord thy God... Thou shall have no other god besides me... Thou shall not kill. Thou shall not commit adultery. Thou shall not steal. Thou shall not bear false witness against thy neighbour...”*³³.

It therefore follows that God is the originator of both the law and the state. It means also that the law and the state is God’s own idea. Man, naturally follow and adopt this divine arrangement under human government. The law is what parliament says it is or what a maximum ruler says it is, depending on the regime. The Supreme Court of Nigeria in *Governor of Lagos State vs. Ojukwu*³⁴ defined law as thus:

“The rules and regulations of a particular country. The rules usually made by the legislative arm of government which order the way persons, bodies and society should behave and, the whole system of rules of a country. One of the most eminent English jurists, Sir Williams Blackstone defined law as the rule of action which is prescribed by some superior and which the inferior is bound to obey”.

The Black’s law dictionary³⁵ defines law as the regime that orders human activities and relations through systematic application of the force of political organized society, or through social pressure backed by force, in such a society³⁶.

Filmer³⁷ argues that Adam was the first king and present kings are or are to be reputed next heir to him. This forms the Theory of divine origin of the state. According to Appadorai³⁸ the will of God is supposed to be made known by revelation mediately or immediately to certain persons who are His earthly vice-regents and by them communicated to the people. Obedience to the state becomes a religious as well as a civil duty; obedience or sacrilege.

King James 1 of England once declared,

“A king can never be monstrously vicious. Even if a king is wicked, it means God has sent him as a punishment for people’s sins and it is unlawful to shake off the burden which God has laid upon them. Patience, earnest prayer and amendment of lives are the only lawful means to move God to relieve them of that heavy curse.”

The purpose of the law has already been discussed to include primarily the preservation or maintenance of law and order in society. The purpose of the state usually represented by the sovereign has been aptly put down by Adams Smith³⁹ in his “Wealth of Nations”⁴⁰ thus: the duty of protecting society from the violence

³¹ These are questions carrying philosophical, religious and social connotations and which have engaged apt attention of jurist philosopher, thinkers and political commentators.

³² Romans 13 verses 1-2

³³ Exodus 20:1-17

³⁴ (1986) 1 NWLR (PT. 18) 621

³⁵ 11th ed. Page 1056

³⁶ This definition of law portrays law as dependent on some measure of force exercisable by the persons who constitute the state as a government.

³⁷ Patriarchal (1680)

³⁸ The substance of politics. Oxford, 1974 P.31

³⁹ He lived between 1723 – 1790

and invasion of other independent societies, the duty of protecting as far as possible, every member of society from the injustice or opposition of every other member of it, or the duty of establishing an exact administration of justice, and the duty of erecting and maintaining certain public works and certain public institutions...

According to Hebert Spencer,⁴¹ the state is nothing but a natural institution for preventing one man from infringing the rights of another. It is a joint stock protection company for mutual assurance.

It is safe therefore to hold and indeed to conclude that the law and the state are set out for same or identical purposes and that both the law and the state need each other for the effective control and harmonization of society for maximum benefit of the maximum number. While it may not hold water that the state is a creation of the law, it creates greater sense to posit that the law is a creation of the state. Hence, it is usually held that the law was made for the people and not the people made for the law. Accordingly, no society can exist in the absence of law and the state, represented by government.

5. LAW AND JUSTICE

The idea of justice in the face of law appears a more or less problematic consideration. This is so because, in most, if not all situations, justice seems or appears to wage war against the law. The face of justice varies considerably from the face of law. Law appears subjective while justice appears objective. Law appears blind while justice sees. This point was well adumbrated by Hon. Justice Rhodes Vivour JSC in *Wassah vs. Karah*⁴².

Where the Supreme Court per the law lord held,

*“Law is blind. It has no eyes, it cannot see. That explains why a statue of a woman with her eyes covered can be found in front of some High Courts. On the contrary, justice is not blind. It has many eyes; it sees and sees very well”*⁴³.

Therefore, it can be safely said that the law has limitations, but justice has no limitations. The territory of law is defined but that of justice is without boundaries. Yes, the court is a court of law, but the court is more of a court of justice than a court of law. This means therefore that the court is prepared and willing to abandon the law in preference for justice where there is a conflict between the two.

The questions that agitate any jurisprudential mind are many; whether a good law guarantees justice or whether a bad law necessarily engenders injustice? Are citizens under any obligation to obey unjust laws? Is having a good judge with bad laws better than having a bad judge with good laws? Who determines a bad law? The questions are endless⁴⁴. Further questions may still be asked; who determines what is justice? What are the parameters for determining justice? Is justice an enemy of the law? Is the law an enemy of justice? Is law a necessary evil for the attainment of justice? Can justice be attained without law? Is there any law in the justice equation?

As Prof Adewale Taiwo⁴⁵ rightly put it, there is no all-embracing or conclusive answer to any of the foregoing questions. Each answer will reflect the intellectual or religious or associational alliance of the proponents and the opponents. This is not surprising because the meanings of the two concepts – Law and Justice are also not settled in their conceptions⁴⁶. In spite of this state of affairs, it suffices to conclude that any law that secures justice in its application is good law.

Prof C.C. Wigwe SAN⁴⁷ puts it more succinctly,

“The relationship between law and justice is a systematic one. A system that makes laws must ensure that justice which means fairness shape that law. Every law in a society must be fair or else that law will not have the legitimacy it deserves... No law can exist without justice. No society can also exist without justice. Justice is justice to the rich, poor and powerful. Without justice there will be no world worth living. It is justice that actually dilutes the brutality of law, especially unjust laws”.

Law wears the face of a monster, but justice has the face of a mistress. When it is said that law should have a human face, it means that law should be conditioned and applied to attain justice.

⁴⁰ Everyday library, ed. Vol. 11 PP 272 – 273

⁴¹ 1820 – 1903

⁴² (2015) 4 NWLR (PT. 1449) 374

⁴³ n.45. 385, ratio 13

⁴⁴ JM Elegido. Jurisprudence 1sted, (spectrum books ltd, 1994) 363 – 365

⁴⁵ Jurisprudence and legal theory in Nigeria. 1sted (Princeton) 2019

⁴⁶ No. 48 PP 37-38

⁴⁷ He is current dean, faculty of law, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

6. LAW AND MORALITY

Two basic questions emerge for determination here. Is law immoral? Is morality lawless? Interrogating the immorality of law is as interesting as interrogating the lawlessness of morality. Between law and morality, which does society really needs or deserves? Without controversy, the languages of law are radically different and diametrically opposed to the languages of morality. The two concepts are clearly of different parents. That is why they both see differently, talk differently and act differently. They both hardly travel in the same boat. This is because their destinations are different. The appeal of law is not and cannot be same as that of morality. They both have eyes, but they see differently. What is morally wrong may not be legally wrong; only what is legally wrong may be punishable by law. Therefore, law do not recognize morality. But often morality has tremendous respect for law.

The clear difference between law and morality was fully captured by the Supreme Court⁴⁸ in the celebrated case of *Attorney-General of the Federation vs. Abubakar*⁴⁹, where the court held thus, “*what is morally reprehensible may not be legally punishable*”⁵⁰. The issue before the court necessitating the quoted pronouncement of the apex court was the morality or otherwise of the behaviour of the then vice president⁵¹ in abandoning the political party upon which platform he contested an election and got elected into office and joining an opposition political party seeking to wrestle political power from his abandoned party in power. The apex court rejected the invitation of the Appellant, to regard the vice president’s behaviour as a legal wrong punishable by law. The court sees the vice president’s behaviour as a moral wrong or a misbehaviour in morality and not as a legal wrong to be punishable in law.

Appadorai⁵² posits that law is the body of rules enforced by government; its ultimate sanction is force. By its very nature, it can control only external acts; it cannot enjoin a spirit⁵³. He identifies two kinds of morality; ideal morality which lies within individual conscience, individual sense of right and wrong, of good and evil. That conscience is largely the expression of custom, social training and religious influence. According to him, individual morality is self-legislating. The second category of morality is positive morality which he describes as the body of rules supported by the prevalent opinion of the community (to which the individual belongs) at any given time.

The most noticeable difference between law and morality can be stated thus;

- a) A violation of the law attracts sanctions from or by the state, but a violation of moral rules only attracts some form of social intolerance.
- b) Law is more definite and consistent than morality which is more of an unwritten code of acceptable behaviour in a particular society to which the individual belongs.
- c) Law is made by an established body and interpreted by another established body. Morality has neither.
- d) Morality is usually coloured or dictated by conscience, training or social upbringing and the individual’s religious inclination. But law operates and applies irrespective of these considerations.
- e) Law dictates but morality appeals.

Therefore, it can be safely concluded that law operates in a different world from morality.

7. LAW AND RELIGION

Law is not and cannot be the same thing as religion. Religion is a spiritual conviction, tailored by certain creeds, of the existence and supremacy of a supreme being which controls and determines life. On the other hand, law is a compulsion to do or to abstain from doing certain things or put up certain behaviours. Religion is self-imposed but law is imposed by force or threat of force. Religion subscribes to ordinances believed by the individual to have emanated from a supreme deity or being whereas law is the product of the ordinances of mere mortals, ordinary men. Law is carnal whereas religion is spiritual. Law governs the physical but religion governs the spiritual. Law operates in the natural, but the province of religion lies more in the supernatural.

⁴⁸ Per. Onnoghen JSC

⁴⁹ (2007) 10 NWLR (PT.1041) 1

⁵⁰ n. 5 @ P. 51 ratio 51

⁵¹ Atiku Abubakar

⁵² The substance of politics, oxford 2004

⁵³ no.55, @ P.64

This is not to say that law has no relationship with religion. This is because almost all the ancient kingdoms and emirates operated Theocracy, thereby rendering no difference between crimes and sins⁵⁴. Many of the laws made in modern western and even African societies are believed to be anchored on the ten commandments handed down to Moses on Mount Sinai or as dictated by Mohammed, the founder of the Islamic religion in the case of Muslim communities in Asia and Africa. As a matter of fact, law making in contemporary societies is often seriously coloured by consideration of the religious inclinations of the members of that society. According to Prof C.C Wigwe⁵⁵.

“Law and religion were also connected in the African traditional societies, there was no separation between the communities and the shrine of the hundreds of gods, spirits and ancestors worshipped then”⁵⁶. The kings of the then African societies exercised both spiritual and secular leadership in the traditional African societies was closely identified with deities, and it was believed that the deities worshipped gave the laws that governed secular societies”.

The three notable religions that dominate the world today are Christianity, Islam and Hinduism. But of the three, Christianity and Islam controls more than ninety percent of the world’s religious faiths. Christianity has stronger roots in the west and some African societies, whereas Islam has roots in the middle east and some African societies. Hindus and Buddhists are mostly found in Asian societies.

In *Barman vs. secular society limited*⁵⁷. Lord summer emphasized that English common law is partly Christian law. In his words,

“Our is, and has always been a Christian state. The English family is built on Christian ideas, and, if the national religion is not Christian, there is none. English law, but we apply many of its principles with equal justice, and equally good government in heathen communities”.

In the same case, another judge⁵⁸ held,

“There is abundant authority for saying that Christianity is part and parcel of laws of the land. But the fact that Christianity is recognized by the law is the basis to an extent for holding that the law will not help endeavours to undermine it”.

Karibi-Whyte JSC⁵⁹ held these views:

“The claim of the Holy Quran to divine revelation is not particular to it. The Holy Bible, which appears to contain the fundamental basis of the common law, claims to have been derived partly from the Ten Commandments God gave to Moses on the mountain. The several books of the Holy Bible are said to have been written on inspiration. The Roman Twelve Table, the laws of the Greeks and the laws operating in many civilized countries are founded on divine revelation”.

It is interesting to note that most written constitutions have accorded due recognition and of course necessary enforcement to the citizen’s right to religious belief and practice. For example, the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria⁶⁰ stipulates clearly thus,

Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in commodity with others, and in public or private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance⁶¹. This clearly demonstrates that religion has become so powerful in society that it has received full recognition and due protection of law. In the same vein, the Holy Bible⁶² and of course the Quran enjoins their adherents to respect and submit to constituted authority and to live lawfully. The ends of the law and religion is the attainment of societal peace and progress; therefore, both have combined to shape the behaviour of man in society. While it is safe to say that law has little or no direct influence on the prescriptions of religion, it is an undeniable truth that law is heavily coloured by the tenets of religious beliefs, practices and doctrines prevalent in the society.

⁵⁴ O. Akin, law and nation building in Nigeria: selected essays (Lagos centre for Political Administration Research, 2005) P. 23

⁵⁵ Dean of law, RSU, Port Harcourt

⁵⁶ n. p. 187

⁵⁷ (1917) Ac 406

⁵⁸ Lord Finlay

⁵⁹ A retired justice of the supreme court of Nigeria, speaking at a judge’s conference; Al-Mustapha journal of law and religion, p. 131

⁶⁰ Section 38

⁶¹ It is one of the fundamental rights enforceable in our law courts.

⁶² Romans 4:13

8. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this discussion is to the effect that amongst all other concepts such as sovereignty, morality, religion, justice and the state, law stands as the leviathan. This is so because law colours the identity and indeed the efficacy of them all. It must however be noted that in certain societies, religion, morality and personal or private inclinations of state actors substantially colour what becomes law. It is also to be said that in contemporary societies, it is very difficult if not impossible for law alone to swim in the waters of society without a corresponding presence of other ideas or concepts.

In other words, law cannot survive alone without the contribution of other concepts or ideas. Law may be the commander in chief, but it must acknowledge the presence and influence of other commanders in the legal order or space. Other concepts breathe in law just as humans breathe in oxygen. Law likewise breathes in other concepts. This is the mystery of survival.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the gamut of debates, arguments and postulations examined in this paper, we are inclined to put forth the following recommendations.

1. The legislature should at all times take into due consideration the moral content and values in society in the course of legislation.
2. The legislature should consider as paramount the need to ensure the enthronement of justice in the law making process.
3. The legislature should always take into cognizance the deep religious values of the society in the law making process. This is more so in societies where a particular religion is predominant.
4. The legislature need to ensure the preservation of the state represented in the person of the sovereign, which in ordinary language is the president or head of government, at all times in the course of their legislative functions.
5. The enactment of just laws should be the pre-occupation of the legislature whereas the just administration of the just laws should be the guiding principle of the enforcers of the just laws.
6. The judex should be bold or courageous enough in the course of adjudication to make pronouncements and decisions that balances the interest of the society.
7. The judex should as much as desirable uphold the balance of justice between the state and the citizens as well as between the poor and the rich and between the powerless and the powerful and of course between the peasant and the poise in the palace.
8. The legislature should make laws with a human face and designed to maintain the cords of the social equilibrium of society.
9. The judex should, in the course of adjudication, resist draconian legislation that tend to reduce the citizenry to the status of slaves or that of prisoners. There is need for a radical judex that will tell the king to his face where he crosses the red line.
10. Finally, the citizenry has to put on the spirit of nationalism with a burning desire to see to it that their society flourishes for the good of all and of posterity. This requires co-operating with the infrastructures of the state, striving for and ensuring fair treatment of fellow citizens.